

Pest management and control WEEDS

New weed host of rice stem nematode identified in Vietnam

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Leersia hexandra has been recognized as a unique weed host of stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*. Fourteen other weeds grow in Mekong Delta rice fields: *Echinochloa colona*, *E. crus-galli*, *Sacciolepis interrupta*, *S. polymorpha*,

S. myosuroides, *Panicum trichoides*, *Brachiaria mutica*, *Fimbristylis littoralis*, *Cyperus iria*, *C. difformis*, *Scirpus grossus*, *Eichhornia crassipes*, *Monochoria hastata*, and *Polygonum scabrum*.

When artificial inoculation methods were used, *D. angustus* attacked two additional weed species — *S. interrupta* and *E. colona*. Degree of infestation and the time needed for symptoms to appear differed.

Two months after inoculation, 80% of

the tillers of *S. interrupta* were infested, with an average 12.5 nematodes/tiller. *E. colona* had 30% diseased tillers with 0.5 nematode/tiller. Control rice variety IR20 had 90% diseased tillers and 17.5 nematodes/tiller. Symptoms appeared 7-8 days after inoculation on *S. interrupta* and IR20, but 10-15 days after on *E. colona*.

S. interrupta could be a secondary host of *D. angustus*, acting as a bond between rice crops. ■

Effect of herbicide weed control on soil microflora in direct-sown, fertilized, wetland rice

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Nine weed control treatments and three fertilizer levels were used on drill-sown IET723 in a split-plot design with 3 replications.

One postemergence spray of propanil at 2 kg ai/ha 15 days after sowing effectively controlled weeds (see table) and was even more effective with supplemental weeding 40 days after sowing. Propanil and butachlor were similar in weed control efficiency in 1973 and 1975, but propanil was significantly better in 1974. Weed growth increased with increased fertilization.

Bacterial populations were higher

than fungal populations in all treatments. There was an initial rise of fungal populations in 2,4-D-treated plots and a drop in butachlor-treated plots. Fungal and bacterial populations were stable in propanil-treated plots. Mid-level fertilizer treatments showed slightly higher populations of fungi and bacteria than did the low fertilizer levels. ■

Effect of weed control treatment and fertilizer level on weed growth and soil microflora in rice, Orissa, India.

Treatment	Dry weight of weeds at harvest (g/50-cm × 50-cm area)			Average fungi population (10 ⁴ /g soil, oven-dry basis) 70 DS	Average bacteria population (10 ⁹ /g soil, oven-dry basis) 70 DS
	1973	1974	1975		
<i>Main plot</i>					
Na salt of 2,4-D @ 1.5 kg a.i./ha	70.0	42.3	97.4	6.0	6.4
Butachlor @ 2.0 kg a.i./ha	51.8	39.3	75.7	4.1	8.6
Na salt of 2,4-D @ 1.5 kg a.i./ha + weeding by weeder at 40 DS	53.9	25.4	77.5	5.7	6.6
Butachlor @ 2.0 kg a.i./ha + weeding by weeder at 40 DS	38.9	24.1	54.0	4.1	8.5
Propanil @ 2.0 kg a.i./ha	49.5	32.5	72.7	5.0	7.7
Propanil @ 2.0 kg a.i./ha + weeding by weeder at 40 DS	29.1	20.1	46.6	5.3	7.7
Propanil @ 2.0 kg a.i./ha + MCPA @ 1.0 kg a.i./ha	44.4	25.6	59.9	5.2	7.7
Conventional farmers' practice ^a	37.0	27.8	62.4	5.2	7.5
Unweeded control	176.3	147.2	272.7	5.1	7.7
CD (0.05)	7.38	6.59	6.59	1.45	1.71
<i>Subplot</i>					
60-30-30 kg NPK/ha	55.6	39.3	83.8	5.2	7.5
90-45-45 kg NPK/ha	60.4	43.4	91.5	5.6	7.8
120-60-60 kg NPK/ha	67.6	45.6	97.6	5.5	7.7
CD (0.05)	2.64	2.03	2.25	0.47	0.54
(Microbial population of basic soil before cropping)				5.2	7.7

^aBlind tillage at 30 DS (days after sowing) with a spike-tooth harrow, followed by 2 hand weedings at 35 and 50 DS.